

Development Strategies of PM A.B.Vajpayee for Indian Structural Development

Paper Id : 18137 Submission Date : 13/09/2023 Acceptance Date : 23/09/2023 Publication Date : 25/09/2023

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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.10209696

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Abstract

India has been commemorating Amrit Kal from the last occasion in 2022. This year, which celebrates the platinum celebration, marks the seventy-fifth anniversary of independence. In light of the current situation, it is imperative to evaluate the contributions made by Prime Minister Atal Bihari Vajpayee, who established a solid framework for organizational capability and structural reforms in thrift. Additionally, he widely opened up the frugality through trade networks and currency surging. The goal of the current paper is to highlight significant initiatives undertaken by Vajpayee throughout his two years as prime minister and to strengthen both the country and the state of Uttar Pradesh. We have focused on infrastructure transformation, disinvestment, and financial caution in this article. Secondary sources of data serve as the paper's foundation. Indicator line based on time series data for roads have been estimated. The article comes to the conclusion that financial restraint, disinvestment in ailing PSUs, and the creation of the National Highway Authority of India were the key tactics that improved Indian frugality. It is unnecessary to mention that UP and Uttarakhand together constitute the two largest nations in the nation.

Keywords Disinvestment, Fiscal Policy, Reforms, Privatization, telecommunication, PSE's.

Introduction

Amrit Utsav is being observed by the thrifty Indians as they mark 75 years of independence. The degree of frugality has expanded and changed over this time. Beginning with the First Five Year Plan in 1956, the country experienced extreme food scarcity, starvation, and suffering. This plan prioritized the expansion of the agricultural sector. The need for capacity structures for industry, particularly significant artificial expansion, was also suddenly understood. Due to this, substantial industrialization was carried out between 1956 and 1961 using main heads, cotton fabric diligence, and sword diligence. In a long-term strategy of Indian planning, this growth process focused on MSMEs, employment addition, poverty reduction, food provisioning, and inclusive metamorphosis was maintained. Major profitable adjustments in Indian planning were desperately needed prior to 1990. Due to these factors, His greatest successes occurred on the business front. He continued the reformist initiatives started by former prime ministers. Later, when Dr. Manmohan Singh succeeded Atal Bihari Vajpayee as Prime Minister in 2004, thriftiness shown extraordinary macroeconomic performance in that the GDP growth rate hit 8 but the affectation stayed well below 4. The foreign exchange reserves rise to previously unheard-of levels. Although Vajpayee had no formal training in economics, he used to involve institutions and experts in the planning process. His efforts on the profitable front helped the BJP project a right-wing image by adhering to the most conservative trends in profitable policy, which were centered on advanced capital investment and capacity structure.

Aim of study

The paper's goal is to highlight PM Vajpayee's significant statements regarding public transportation, telecommunications infrastructure, privatization, and financial deficit management. The information is secondary information that can be found in eye-catching government reports from key organizations. The information is limited to AB Vajpayee's Prime Ministry. The secondary data is statistically recycled. Here are the Vajpayee Government's four most significant financial, infrastructure, and business reforms.

1. Construction of roads

2. Telecom Development
3. Privatization and disinvestment
4. Fiscal Policy Reforms.

Review of Literature

According to Ahluwalia (2018), the government under Vajpayee opened the insurance business to foreign investment by letting foreign players to take up to 49 of the stock in a joint venture with an Indian establishment, despite the glacial speed of decision-making.

According to Mishra (2018), Vajpayee will also be remembered for launching both large and small structural systems, including the ambitious plan to build roads that connect the four major metropolises of New Delhi, Mumbai, Kolkata, and Chennai. Additionally, he had the idea of building a road made of charcoal or concrete that would run through every town in the nation during rainy seasons in order to provide pastoral areas the structure they needed. Har Khet Ko Pani, Har Hath ko Kaam (every ranch be rinsed and every hand has worked), and a firm focus on the issues relating to youths and growers in formative association with cutting-edge skills and technological knowledge under the motto Jai Jawan, Jai Kisan, Jai Vigyan (Hail the Youth, Hail the Farmers, Hail the Science) were some of the things Sharma (2018, p. 3) mentioned in his vision.

According to Kumari (2021), the Golden Quadrilateral Plan, which connected the major metropolises from the North to the South and from the East to West was the most important activity of the Vajpayee time. She says that while some design work might have been finished during his administration, most substantial work would have to wait until later.

N.M.P.Verma (2023), concluded that FRBM played an important role in reducing the fiscal deficit while still attempting to meet the 4% target. The current year budget 2023-24 put a fiscal deficit of 5.9%, which is very high and hence needs disciplinary measures. The post-Vajpayee period also followed his path of highway extension, connectivity extension, fiscal deficit management, and disinvestment.

Main Text

Major Policy Initiatives

Road Construction

National highways provide essential connectivity to urban and rural areas and are the backbone of any country's transportation system. India needs a strong and extensive network of roads to keep up with development given its quickly increasing frugality. One of India's most renowned politicians, Atal Bihari Vajpayee, presided as prime minister from 1998 to 2004.

He made a substantial contribution to the transformation of India's road and transportation system during his tenure. A frugality that he inherited was struggling to keep up with the rest of the world. Particularly in need of an upgrade was the transportation industry. The country's infrastructure, including its road system, was in disarray. Vajpayee acknowledged the necessity to deal with these problems and started various businesses that would change India's transportation industry. He is renowned for his contributions to the country's structural advancement and prosperous expansion. . During his tenure as Prime Minister, Vajpayee launched several initiatives aimed at improving the transportation and road infrastructure in the country. Public-private hookups(PPP) were encouraged, and colorful models were introduced to make investment in the sector more seductive. The government also established the National Highways Authority of India(NHA) in 2002 to oversee the development of roadways in the country. The major enterprise taken are-

1. Pradhan Mantri Gram Sadak Yojana(PMGSY)

The Pradhan Mantri Gram Sadak Yojana (PMGSY), introduced by Vajpayee in 2000, was one of his most major business ventures. The goal of this plan was to connect all of the country's townlets with rain roads. The program was designed to provide connectivity to the nation's rural regions and aid in the development of pastoral areas. Over 5 lakh km of roads have been built as part of this program, and over 1 lakh habitations are now connected to all-weather highways.

2. Project for Development of National Highways

Additionally, in 1998, Vajpayee launched the National Highways Development Project (NHDP). This project was designed to connect important cities, ports, and industrial districts by widening and improving the existing roadways and building new ones. The Golden Quadrilateral project, which sought to link four significant Indian cities, was finished in 2006. The project took a record six years to complete and spanned a distance of 5,846 kilometers. The NHDP was broken down into seven phases, and the government set a goal of building 7,000 km of roadways annually. By the end of 2010, the entire length of national highways had grown to almost 71,000 km, and it reached 132,500 km in 2018–19.

3. The Golden Quadrilateral

The Golden Quadrilateral design was one of Vajpayee's most important ventures. This plan used roads to connect the four major metropolises of Delhi, Mumbai, Chennai, and Kolkata. The design traveled 5,846 kilometres and was finished six times faster than the previous record. The Golden Quadrilateral improved connection between the major metropolises and gave the areas it covered a boost for successful expansion.

Telecom Growth

Private investments helped the cellular telephone business become competitive, and the Value-Added Services (VAS) market also allowed for private participation. During this time, the Narasimha Rao administration introduced the National Telecommunications Policy (NTP), which overhauled the ownership, management, and regulation of telecommunications infrastructure. The approach aimed to bring telecommunication services to every Indian hamlet and promoted the concept of universal access to telecommunications. Plans for the deregulation of fundamental telecom services were also part of this agenda. They were also effective in establishing alliances between foreign businesses and state-owned telecom providers. A total of 49% of the share was available to international corporations. The multinational corporations were solely interested in transferring technology; they were not involved in establishing policies.

The international organizations IMF and World Bank urged the Indian government to liberalize long-distance teleservices in order to break the state-owned fleck and VSNL's monopolies and open the market to competition in the long-distance carrier market. This would help reduce rates and improve the country's frugality. Instead, the Rao-led government liberalized original services to win over opposition parties and ensure foreign participation in the long-distance assiduity in later years. Twenty telecom circles were created for the country's initial phone service, and 18 telecom circles were created for mobile service. Two service providers were allowed to operate in the cellular service member per circle, and each was issued a 15- time license. The government encountered opposition from the ITI, DoT, MTNL, VSNL, and other labor unions during all of these improvements, but they were able to overcome every obstacle.

The telecom policy of the NDA government under Vajpayee, which was published in 1999, opened the door for structural reforms in the industry, resulting in a record-breaking increase in mobile subscribers, the entry of competition into the wireless tele-services sector, and a number of deeply ingrained nonsupervisory reforms, which were also encouraged by a correction to the TRAI Act, 1999. Rather than requiring customers to cover fixed expenses, the new telecom policy of 1999 allowed companies to offer mobile services on a profit-share basis. He was constantly motivated by the idea that liberalization would allow us to celebrate our lucrative eventuality and, in the end, prepare the way for our country to establish itself as an encyclopedically competitive, strong, and prosperous nation. He was a great profitable leftist.

In 1997, the government established the Telecom Regulatory Authority of India (TRAI), ending government involvement in pricing and program development. New political forces entered the picture in 1999, and Atal Bihari Vajpayee's new government promoted reforms and improved liberalization policies.

The Telecom controversies agreement and Appellate Tribunal was established by the Vajpayee administration in 2000 with an amendment to the TRAI Act 1997. The Department of Telecommunication Services (DTS), which later adopted the name Bharat Sanchar Nigam Ltd. (BSNL), corporately renamed the fleck's operations division. The proposal to enhance the foreign investors' 49 percent stake to 74 percent was rejected by the opposing political parties and socialist thinkers. The country's business organisations pushed the government to privatize VSNL. Finally, in April 2002, the government decided to lower the control it held over VSNL from 53 to 26 and make it available for sale to

private companies. In the end, TATA bought a 25 percent interest in VSNL. Numerous foreign investors used this as a point of entry into the Indian telecom industry. According to legend, the last two decades have been the astuteness' "golden age," with rapid-fire improvements. in demand, legislation, and technology. India has the second-largest telecom customer base in the world, and it has rapidly grown in recent years. A key factor in the sector's explosive growth has been the combination of high consumer demand with liberal and reformist plans.

Exports of mobile phones increased by \$5 billion in just seven months, with phone shipments more than doubling year over year between April and October. This is more than twice as much money as India made in the same period of 2017 (\$2.2 billion). India will have 920 million unique mobile users by 2025, of whom 88 million will be 5G subscribers, making it the second-largest smartphone market worldwide. According to the GSMA, this is. Additionally, it is predicted that between 2023 and 2040, 5G technology will significantly increase India's thriftiness by \$450 billion. India has added approximately 500 million new Smartphone addicts in the past ten years. There will be 850 million Smartphone addicts by 2026, or about 55 percent of the population. The Department of Telecommunications (2023) intends to create a 30 lakh km fiber-optic cable network with an average download speed of 25 Mbps and 100 broadband access points, according to its Annual Report. 55 fiberization of movable halls in rural locations. From 61 million in March 2014 to 816 million in September 2022, the number of broadband connections climbed by 1238. The plan is to fiberize 70 buildings by the end of 2024, providing an average internet speed of 50 MBPS and rolling out 50 lakh kilometers of fiber optic cable over the entire country of India. The Network Readiness Index 2022 places India in the 61st position, moving up six spots. India also comes in second place in terms of "International Internet Bandwidth" and "Mobile Broadband Internet Business within the country." India is third in the world in terms of "Domestic Request Size" and "Annual Investment in Dispatches Services."

By the end of January 2023, 5G services had been activated across all authorized service zones in 238 metropolises. In the global rankings for average mobile pets, India climbs 10 species, from 69th in January 2023 to th in December.

Privatization and Disinvestment

For the first 40 years after gaining independence, the nation decided to follow a development path in which the public sector operated as the profitable machine. The public sector continued to outgrow itself, and its excesses became apparent in the sector's low capacity for application and low effectiveness as a result of overstaffing, poor work ethics, overcapitalization as a result of significant time and cost overruns, a lack of innovation, an inability to form quick and timely opinions, a significant delay in the decision-making process, etc. On the other hand, the private sector started to indicate signals of expansion. As a result, the choice to implement the Disinvestment plan was decided in 1991.

India started to change in 1991–1992, when 31 PSUs were selected and sold for a total of Rs. 3038 crores. The Disinvestment Commission, which was established in August 1996 to direct, oversee, monitor, and publicize the gradual disinvestment of Indian PSUs, was presided over by G. V. Ramakrishna. 13 research were included, and they offered suggestions for privatizing 57 PSUs. Later, in July 2001, Dr. R.H. Patil took charge of this commission. Disinvestment received more attention during the Vajpayee administration. The Disinvestment Commission, however, stopped operating in May 2004.

The Department of Disinvestment was created as a separate department by the Vajpayee administration in December 1999, and the Ministry of Disinvestment followed suit in September 2001. In May 2004, the Ministry of Finance added the Department of Disinvestment to its departments. From 1991–1992 to 2000–2001, a total of Rs. 54300 crore was intended to be raised by PSU disinvestment; however, the government was only able to raise less than half of that amount, or Rs. 20078.62 crore. It's important to note that only three out of ten months saw a government meeting. In 1993–1994 there were no PSU disinvestment proceeds over the expected amount of Rs.3500 crore.

The following are some of the major causes of similar little or minimal consumption:

- 1)Unpredictable request conditions,
- 2)Private Players setting up the monstrous trade offer,
- 3)Controversial valuation of PSEs,

- 4) Persistent Policy Nebulosity,
- 5) Large-scale Trade Union and Worker Rejections,
- 6) Transparency Issues, Missing or Weak Political Will

The trade of nonage holdings in the PSEs through the distribution of shares for trade to domestic and international investors generated the disinvestment proceeds realized during this time. In fact, because the government controlled well-known companies like IOC, BPCL, HPCL, GAIL, and VSNL, the value obtained by trading shares was minimal. Most of these nonage stake proposals were accepted by domestic financial institutions during this time. The Unit Trust of India was one such significant institution.

1. NDA Administration (1997–1998 to 2003–2004)

2)1 During this time, significant disinvestments were made by Vajpayee's administration. These either came in the shape of strategic agreements conforming to an efficient transfer of operation control to private investors or a trade offer to the general public, with the government maintaining control of the power. Between 1980 and 1989, the financial deficit was 6.5% on average. The financial shortage was somewhat reduced after the LPG policy went into effect in 1991, but from 2004 to 2021, it significantly decreased once the FRBM Act went into effect. From 2004 to 2014, the financial deficit was around 4.6 of GDP, and from 2014 to 2022, it was, on average, 4.8 of GDP. FRBM attempts to achieve the three target goals while also assisting in reducing the financial imbalance.

2. Congress (UPA) Government (2004-2005 to 2013-2014)

The issue of disinvestment became more politically conflicting during the UPA-I regime. It led to a virtual halt of the exercise during this period. Only Rs.8515.93 Crore in total were received from disinvestments in the five years from 2003-04 to 2008-09. The disinvestment proceeds, however, showed a much larger volume during the UPA-II government, amounting to Rs.84208 Crore during the four-year period from 2009-10 to 2012-13.

1. NDA Government (2013-2014 to 2022-2023)

A renewed focus on disinvestments was initially caused by a stable administration and better stock market circumstances. Minority holdings in listed and unlisted (profit-making) PSUs were sold by the government as the process's initial step. By making open offers during this time period, disinvestments were made in businesses like REC, NMDC, SJVN, EIL, CIL, MOIL, and NHPC Ltd. Also, compared to a target of Rs.175000 crore, final realizations fell to Rs.15440 crore (revised target: Rs.78000 crore in 2021-2022).

Fiscal Policy Reforms

Economic Survey was defined there as "the excess of government expenditure and net lending over current revenues." The term "fiscal deficit" is now frequently used to describe the government's deficit budget. Economists and analysts keep a close eye on the phrase, which has been frequently used to describe the financial health of the country. The government also views this as one of the most significant statistics and, in addition to publishing it along with other budgetary data, computes the expected fiscal deficit when it presents its annual budget. It also offers guidance on what the anticipated level of the fiscal deficit would be in the upcoming years.

Large and ongoing fiscal deficits are generally considered detrimental to strong macroeconomic outcomes by policymakers and other decision-makers. Such deficits frequently discourage private investment, raise the risk of inflation, weaken the balance of payments (BoP), complicate financial sector reform, and place a debt burden on future generations. The fiscal deficit is one of the challenges India has faced since gaining independence. India's fiscal deficit averaged 6-7% during the 1990s, never dropping below 3%. The government attempted to address this issue, but it did not adopt any measures that would lower the fiscal deficit below 3%. The Vajpayee government took the initiative towards fiscal consolidation, and on August 26, 2003, the Fiscal Responsibility and Budget Management Act (FRBMA) was enacted by the Parliament of India. The Act became operational on July 5, 2004. The FRBM Act specifies goals and suggests strategies for reducing revenue and budgetary deficits. It proposed yearly targets to

gradually reduce fiscal and revenue deficits in order to achieve the targeted debt-to-GDP ratio.

All of the government's outstanding liabilities are referred to as debt, while the fiscal deficit refers to fresh borrowing during the year and the revenue shortfall to the extent that these fresh borrowings were used to cover revenue expenses. Savings in the public sector increased as a result, rising from -0.8% of GDP in FY 2000.

India first experienced issues with its balance of payments in the middle of the 1980s. India's oil import bill increased, exports declined, financing dried up, and investors withdrew their capital as a result of the Gulf War. Over time, large fiscal deficits produced a cascading effect on the trade imbalance that resulted in an external payments crisis. At the end of the 1980s, India's economy was in dire straits. After introducing the LPG policy in 1991, it decreased the fiscal deficit to some extent, but not much. So, in 1999, the Vajpayee government launched an initiative to address the issue of the fiscal deficit and introduced the FRBM Act, which set a goal of 3% of the fiscal deficit after being put into effect. Despite the fact that the budget deficit increased during the financial crisis of 2008, The COVID-19 pandemic issue has reemerged, and the country's economic deficit, which is currently between 6-7% of GDP, remains beyond normal. Yet, since 2004, the FRBM strategy has had a substantial impact on decreasing the fiscal deficit problem since we have used a normal period.

Fiscal deficit varies during the periods corresponding to different governments. During the 1980-89 period, the fiscal deficit was on average 6.5%. After implementing the LPG policy in 1991, some reduction was seen, but after implementing the FRBM Act, there is a high decline in the fiscal deficit during the 2004 to 2021 period. In the period 2004 to 2014, the fiscal deficit was at around 4.6%, and between the 2014 to 2022 period, it was, on average, at 4.8% of GDP. Thus, FRBM plays an important role in reducing the fiscal deficit while still attempting to meet the 3% target.

Conclusion

The contributions made by Atal Bihari Vajpayee to the growth of India's transportation industry are impressive. The development of the country has been forever changed by his vision and dedication to improving the structure. His business transformed India's outdated road system, improved connectivity, produced employment openings, and accelerated profitable growth.

Second, his legacy persisted and inspired future administrations to disinvest and manage financial deficit in order to achieve a better and more profitable frugality. In order to enhance liquidity and lessen fiscal stress in the telecom sector, extensive structural and procedural reforms were put into effect in 2021. The financial deficit was, on average, 6.5 throughout the years 1980–1989 in this period. Some reductions were observed in the time following the implementation of liberal, privatization, and globalization policies in 1991, but after the FRBM Act came into effect, we may observe a significant decrease in the financial shortage in the years 2004 to 2021. The financial deficit was roughly 4.59 in the years 2004 to 2014 and 4.82 in the years 2014 to 2022. FRBM played a significant role in lowering the deficit while attempting to meet the four targets. The financial deficiency in the present time budget for 2023–2024 was 5.9, which is egregiously high and requires corrective action. The post-Vajpayee era likewise continued his trajectory of disinvestment, trace extension, connectivity expansion, and financial insufficiency operation.

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P: ISSN No. 2394-0344

RNI No. UPBIL/2016/67980

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